

A survey on applying handcrafted and learned feature extraction for breast cancer classification using machine learning and deep learning algorithms

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Abstract- In recent years, breast cancer has become a condition that affects more and more people. Because it can spread from the breast to other regions of the body, it is the second most common cause of mortality for women. Therefore, early detection is essential for effective treatment. Expert systems can assist in the precise detection and categorization of benign tumours utilising data mining and machine learning approaches, avoiding the need for needless therapies. This study examines the application of learned and hand-crafted features in deep learning and machine learning models for the detection of breast cancer. There are numerous models for computer-aided diagnostics that offer different applications for these methods. This review explores different breast cancer detection methods and compares their accuracies while summarizing their findings, challenges, and limitations. Overall, automated feature extraction and classification algorithms can assist medical practitioners in diagnosing and detecting breast cancer, improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: breast cancer, machine learning, deep learning, computer-aided diagnosis (CAD)

I. INTRODUCTION

Gene abnormalities lead to cancer development. The nucleus of every cell contains the genes, and our bodies' cells replace themselves in a systematic manner through cell proliferation. However, mutations can alter cell growth, the capacity to continue dividing without restriction or order, and the propensity to produce a benign or malignant tumour. Around 2.7 million persons in the United States are estimated to have the condition, according to information in Cancer Statistics, 2020 [1]. Over 13.9 lakh new cases of cancer are recognised each year, and 8.5 lakh cancer-related deaths are reported. For men and women, respectively, the risk of dying from cancer is roughly 4,38,297 and 4,13,381 respectively. Oral cavity, stomach, and lung cancer were found to be the causes of 25% of cancer deaths in men, and uterine cervix, breast, and oral cavity cancer were the causes of 25% of cancer deaths in women.

According to Global Cancer Statistics 2020, [2], there were around 10.0 million cancer deaths and 19.3 million new cancer cases in 2020. A thorough breakdown of cancer cases in 2020 is shown in Fig. 1. As we can see, breast cancer accounts for 11.7% of all malignancies in women and is the most common carcinoma. According to the Globocan 2020 study [3], there were 684,996 fatalities and 2,261,419 new cases of breast cancer.

Achieving a great quality of life is challenging when cancer strikes older people [4]. Ageing is the biggest risk factor for both different types of cancer and cancer in general. Cancer incidence rates increase steadily with age, from less than 25 cases per 100,000 people under the age of 20 to approximately 350 per 100,000 people in the 45-49 age range to more than 1,000 per 100,000 people in the 60+ age range [5]. The incidence rates of all cancer types by various ages are displayed in Fig. 2. The population in the United States (U. S.) aged 85 to 94 years comprised

1.6% of the total population in 2010 and had grown by 30% between 2000 and 2010 [1]. The number of cancer diagnoses among senior Americans (those in the 85+ age category) has increased as a result of improved cancer screening techniques and the U.S. population's longer life expectancy. 7.7% of all cancers in the US between 2005 and 2009 were cancer.

This survey focuses on current advances in machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) approaches for the early identification of breast cancer. It illustrates the advantages and disadvantages of various research techniques, difficulties, and potential paths for future study. CAD systems are created to categorise benign and malignant lesions and automate the identification of breast cancer. With the help of ML and DL algorithms, algorithms have been developed that can more reliably diagnose the condition at an earlier stage, reducing the frequency of readmissions to hospitals and clinics. Thus, using AI approaches can facilitate the development of new fidelity protocols in healthcare and lower healthcare expenses resulting from incorrect diagnoses.

Figure1.Global Cancer Statistics 2020

Figure 2. Incidence rates by age at diagnosis, all cancer types[14]

A. *Breast Cancer*

Breast cancer arises from uncontrolled growth of breast cells. It commonly originates in the lobules or ducts of the breast, responsible for milk production and transportation. In rarer cases, it can develop from the stromal tissues, including fatty and fibrous tissues. Cancer cells can progressively invade nearby healthy breast tissue and reach the underarm lymph nodes, which act as detectors of foreign substances. If cancer cells enter the lymph nodes, they have a potential pathway to spread to other organs. Breast cancer is recognized by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the most prevalent cancer among women and a leading cause of cancer-related deaths in women. Breast cancer has emerged as the most prevalent illness affecting women today and a leading cause of death. In order to save a person's life, cancer must be diagnosed and treated early. 1.7 million women developed cancer in 2012, according to the data [6]. People's inability to recognise diseases at an early stage affects the death rate day by day, as is the case with any healthcare [7]. According to the statistics provided at www.breastcancerindia.net, 144937 women had breast cancer identified, and 70218 of them had passed away from it [8]. It is challenging to determine the precise diagnosis even when a different test is carried out. Numerous researchers have identified numerous automated breast cancer detection techniques. A few examples, like as CAD (Computer Aided Tool), are also used by doctors. Most Indian women, both in urban and rural areas, are affected by breast cancer, which is a common disease. The type of cancer tissue is determined using a variety of ML and DL methods. Unlike malignant conditions, which are cancerous and can be fatal, benign conditions do not pose a threat to human life. Even though technology has advanced, 20% of women worldwide still pass away each year [9]. The effectiveness of prediction illness models can be improved by enhancing the knowledge data with the help of developing approaches like machine learning and deep learning [10]. The fundamental motivation for the work discussed in this paper is the growing dangers of breast cancer shown by earlier research, which pushes us to explore unresolved and challenging questions. Breast cancer first manifests as a dangerous lump, and as it progresses, it grows uncontrollably and inconsistently. Even though technology has advanced, it is still unknown what causes breast cancer. Pathologists can find it through a few typical risk variables that affect women. Sometimes this disease is thought to have characteristics that come from the patient's genetic makeup. The two main types of breast cancer treatment are often local and symmetric. According to a World Health Organisation survey, 96% of women with cancer may live for an average of 5 years if they receive an early diagnosis.

B. *Cancer Categorization*

There are two types of breast cancer: invasive and non-invasive/in situ. Non-invasive breast cancer cannot spread to or grow into other body regions, but invasive breast cancer begins in the milk ducts and can do so. Invasive ductal carcinoma and invasive lobular carcinoma are the two most prevalent kinds of invasive breast cancer. The most common type of cancer, invasive ductal carcinoma, begins in the milk ducts of the breast and has the potential to spread to the breast's surrounding tissues.

Invasive lobular carcinoma originates in lobules before spreading to other body regions. Invasive ductal carcinoma, the second most frequent type of breast cancer after invasive ductal carcinoma, is the most typical type. Breast cancer comes in a variety of forms, including Phyllodes tumour, angiosarcoma, inflammatory breast carcinoma, Paget's disease of the breast, triple-negative breast carcinoma, and non-invasive breast cancer. Non-

invasive breast cancer cells stay in one area of the breast and don't invade other organs, lobes, or ducts. Ductal carcinoma and lobular carcinoma are the two forms of in situ malignancies.

Ductal carcinoma is a non-invasive carcinoma in which the cancer cells are confined to the ductal system and have not moved to the adjacent breast tissue. Non-invasive carcinoma is referred to as lobular carcinoma when cancer cells have spread within the milk-producing glands rather than the surrounding tissues.

C. Progression Stages of Cancer

The breast cancer stage describes the extent of the cancer cells' invasion outside of the primary tumour. It depends on a number of variables, such as the tumor's size and location as well as whether the disease has spread to other parts of the body [11]. Breast cancer is classified into five primary phases, as shown in Table 1 [12].

TABLE 1
STAGES OF BREAST CANCER

Cancer Stages	Description
Stage 0	The disease is non-invasive. This means abnormal cells are present but have not grown beyond your breast ducts.
Stage I	The cancer cells extend to the nearby breast tissue and are confined only to the lobules and ducts of the breast.
Stage II	The tumor is either smaller than 2 cm or larger than 5 cm and may or may not affect the nearby lymph nodes.
Stage III	Cancer has invaded nearby tissue and lymph nodes at this stage but hasn't spread to distant organs.
Stage IV	Cancer has extended to areas away from your breast, such as your bones, liver, lungs, or brain.

D. Datasets

Table 2 lists the publicly accessible datasets that researchers have recently used.

TABLE 2
DATABANKS

Data repository	Dataset name	Description
Breast Histology [13]	Bioimaging Challenge 2015 Breast Histology Dataset	The dataset contains 269 histology images of breast cancer that have been stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E). These images have a resolution of 2048×1536 pixels. The dataset includes images from four different groups: normal breast tissue, benign breast conditions, in situ breast cancer, and invasive breast cancer.
BACH's dataset[14]	ICIAR 2018 - Grand Challenge on Breast Cancer Histopathology images dataset	There are 400 total photos in the dataset, which have been divided into 100 normal classes, 100 benign classes, 100 classes of in situ carcinomas, and 100 classes of invasive carcinomas.
CAMELYON16[15]	CAMELYON16 challenge dataset	There are 400 whole-slide pictures (WSIs) of sentinel lymph nodes in this challenge data set, which was compiled from two different datasets. Both the University Medical Centre Utrecht and Radboud University Medical Centre in Nijmegen, the Netherlands, have collected the data.

CAMELYON17[15]	CAMELYON17 challenge dataset	Lesion-level training data from CAMELYON16, which was gathered from Radboud UMC and UMC Utrecht, will be used for CAMELYON17. Additionally, there are lesion-level annotations for 10 training slides from each of the 50 annotated medical centres in CAMELYON17.
Cancer Metastases in Lymph Nodes Challenge[15]	Breast cancer metastasis detection dataset for the Cancer Metastases in Lymph Nodes Challenge	The combined dataset consists of images from the CAMELYON16 and CAMELYON17 challenges. The images in this dataset have dimensions ranging from approximately 1×105 to 2×105 pixels at the highest resolution. The main task in this dataset is classification, where each image is labeled as either normal tissue or metastases. There are two sets of training datasets within this combined dataset. The first set comprises a total of 170 images, with 100 images belonging to the normal class and 70 images in the metastases class. The second set consists of 100 images, with 60 images in the normal class and 40 images in the metastases class.
MITOS-ATYPIA-14 [16]	MITOS-ATYPIA-14 dataset	1539×1376 -pixel images of breast cancer on (H&E)-stained slides at 20 and 40 times magnification. A testing set contains 496 images obtained from 5 distinct breast biopsies and a training set has 1200 images obtained from 16 different breast biopsies.
TUPAC16 [17]	TUPAC16 dataset	The dataset comprises of 73 histopathology images of breast cancer at a magnification level of $40 \times$ from three Netherlands-based pathology facilities. The dataset consists of 50 training images that are 5657×5657 pixels in size and 23 test images that are 2000×2000 pixels in size. It was assembled from two different pathology centres. The training dataset's images are later randomly cropped to 2000 by 2000 pixels in size.
UCIMLR/University of California Irvine Machine Learning Repository[18]	Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) Data Set	WBCD is a commonly used multivariate classification dataset among researchers working on machine learning research. It contains 569 instances with 32 attributes.
BreakHis[19]	Breast Cancer Histopathological Database	It includes 9,109 microscopic pictures of breast tumour tissue taken at different magnifications ($40 \times$, $100 \times$, $200 \times$, and $400 \times$) from 82 individuals. In PNG format (700×460 pixels, 3-channel RGB, 8-bit depth per channel), it currently stores 2,480 benign and 5,429 malignant samples.
SEER[20]	SEER Breast Cancer Data	It contains stage-by-stage survivorship statistics for breast cancer and SEER incidence and population data correlated with age, sex, race, year of diagnosis, and geographic locations

E. Breast Cancer Diagnosis Techniques

Breast cancer diagnosis is a multimodal process that typically involves physical examinations by the patient and physician, breast screening methods, and other diagnostics. Breast cancer can be diagnosed using a variety of methods [21]. Table 3 lists some of the classic and cutting-edge techniques that researchers have recently employed [22-25].

TABLE 3
TRADITIONAL AND EMERGING TECHNIQUES

Techniques	Pros	Cons
SBE-Self-Breast examination	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Raises public consciousness 2. May execute this simple technique at home. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise breast cancer early 2. Significant amounts of overdiagnosis and false positives
CBE-Clinical Breast examination	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduced breast cancer mortality. 2. Can detect breast cancer missed by mammography. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. An increase in false-positive findings. 2. Excessive levels of overdiagnosis and false positives.
Screen Film Mammography (SFM)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifies cancer in its earliest stages 2. Common modality 3. High sensitivity for fatty-tissue-filled breasts 4. It is affordable 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Low sensitivity and thick breast 2. Nondigital
Full Field Digital Mammography (FFDM)/Digital Mammography (D.M.)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High specificity and sensitivity in detecting cancer at an early stage 2. Effective and standard modality 3. Mobile equipment 4. Temporal reaction (around one minute) 5. Reliable resolution 6. Greater accuracy with digital mammography in thick breasts 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High specificity and sensitivity in detecting cancer at an early stage 2. Effective and standard modality 3. Mobile equipment 4. Temporal reaction (around one minute) 5. Reliable resolution 6. Greater accuracy with digital mammography in thick breasts
Ultrasound (U.S.)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High diagnostic value in breast-dense women 2. Mobile equipment 3. No radiation is present. 4. It is appropriate for pregnant ladies. 5. Low-cost, reliable, and secure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High false-positive rates 2. Poor contrast 3. Operator dependent biases 4. Incorrectly indicates a negative result
Magnetic resource imaging (MRI)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Almost maximal sensitivity 2. Can identify cancer that has spread intraductally 3. Optimal contrast 4. High quality 5. Nonionizing radiation 6. Applied to patients at high risk 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Specificity values are lower, and variables require suitable equipment. 2. Biopsies can be challenging. 3. Imaging is limited to the breast's lateral side. 4. Not transportable 5. Expensive gadget. 6. Possibility of a false-positive outcome 7. High body temperature may during long MR
PET/CT Imaging	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It is accurate to register and fuse images. 2. Effective contrast 3. Relevant details 4. Extremely sensitive 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Makes use of radiation with ions 2. Employed radioisotopes 3. Lack of clarity 4. The stationary gadget 5. Expensive gadget

Digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT)/3D mammography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifies cancer in dense breasted women 2. Decrease the number of false negatives and positives 3. Several 3D images are shown at a single screening 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Costly 2. Compared to D.M., the average radiation dose is one to two times higher.
Thermography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prompt detection 2. Noninvasive 3. Not radiation-emitting 4. Rapid reaction 5. The ideal imaging technique for thick breasts. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sensitive to changes in room temperature 2. There are many false negatives and false positives 3. Limited Specificity
Electrical impedance tomography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Noninvasive 2. Nonradioactive 3. Relatively inexpensive 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Poor spatial resolution
Histopathology (H.P.) images	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use multi-color pictures to diagnose various cancer types rather than only detecting malignancy. 2. Tissues are capable of being thoroughly studied. 3. Due to the creation of several region-of-interest (ROI) images from slide images, there is a reduced risk of missing cancer in its early stages. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Because manual analysis is laborious and time-consuming, high proficiency is necessary. 2. Colour fluctuation and various staining techniques might lead to incorrect diagnosis
Microwave imaging	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Minimally invasive 2. Not radioactive 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inadequate resolution at greater depth 2. Fibro glandular tissues with low contrast
Optical imaging	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cheap, non-radioactive, and transportable 2. Rapid reaction 3. Strong contrast 4. Safe 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Low contrast due to high dispersion 2. Insufficient imaging depth 3. Less spatial resolution

F. Advantages of Histological BC Image Classification

Large-format histopathology offers definite advantages over conventional routine pathology methods because it preserves the spatial relationships between the tumour components and their relationships to the resection margins. In this article, we present a series of 1000 consecutive breast cancer patients that were investigated using large-format histology and meticulous radiological-pathological correlation. The representation of a tumour based on how significantly the tumour tissues differ from normal tissue is known as histological classification of cancer. The hematoxylin-eosin (HE) stained histopathology picture is frequently acknowledged as a best practise for predicting and assessing the prognosis of breast cancer. Information about the biological traits and clinical behaviours of BC is affordable and predictive.

II. COMPUTER AIDED CANCER DIAGNOSIS

Radiologists are increasingly relying on computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) as a tool for analysing mammograms. Several research teams are developing CAD systems to categorise benign and malignant tumours. Ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging tests are frequently advised to characterise breast lesions found either clinically or during screening. There have recently been more CAD apps created for screening mammography, but more are

being tested for ultrasound and MRI breast imaging. The next generation of CAD systems will include CAD characterisation as a key element.

The technology of CAD is used to identify and characterise cancer. Although CAD is not restricted to a single form of disease, many CAD systems have been created and used for breast cancer up to this point. This review will go over how CAD systems are now used to diagnose breast cancer, how they are used as a second reader in clinical settings, and research that have looked at how CAD affects radiologists' performance. For various imaging modalities, many CAD applications are being created. Due to commercially available, FDA-approved devices, screen-film mammography has been the primary clinical application of CAD to date. Numerous research have demonstrated how CAD enhances radiologists' abilities. Many academic institutions have invested a significant amount of research time in creating CAD techniques. As a second reader, CAD systems will take on a greater significance in the clinic. Clinical studies have demonstrated that CAD can increase the precision of the identification of breast cancer. Preclinical research has shown that CAD has the ability to more accurately classify malignant and benign tumours. For various breast-imaging modalities, more and more CAD systems are being created. The diagnosis of breast cancer using histopathological pictures has recently piqued the research community's interest. The biggest labelled publicly accessible dataset, "BreKHis," including 7909 histopathological pictures of both benign and malignant classifications, was made available by the authors [26]. Since then, a large number of academics and professionals have studied the BreKHis dataset to create automated and trustworthy methods to separate various breast cancer histological images utilising CNNs as the basic building models. To undertake evaluative comparisons in the next sections, we exclusively present a systematic review of recently published publications that examined the BreKHis dataset for MD and MI breast cancer classifications. Spanhol et al. [27] trained a deep CNN model, which is a subset of AlexNet [28], using a set of pixel patches from histopathology pictures. These patches, with sizes of 32×32 and 64×64 , were extracted using sliding window and random strategy approaches. Then, utilising sum, product, and maximum procedures, the final probabilities of these patches were used to classify benign and cancerous breast tissues. The highest degree of accuracy was attained between 80.8% and 89.6%. The same authors looked into the utility of employing deep features (DeCAF) derived from a pre-trained CNN (BVLC CaffeNet), then used them as inputs to train a logistic regression classifier in their subsequent study [29]. Their findings demonstrated that DeCAF characteristics might be a practical substitute for a CNN trained from scratch, reaching an accuracy for benign and malignant classification between 81.6% and 84.8%. 'Single task' and 'multi-task' are two distinct CNN-based designs that Bayramoglu et al. [30] introduced. While the multi-task was utilised to predict both the malignancy and the magnification factor simultaneously, the single task was made to predict the malignancy alone. According to the patient level score, the reported accuracy when using the single-task CNN ranged from 82.10% to 84.63% and when using the multi-task CNN, it ranged from 80.69% to 83.39%. BiCNN is a revolutionary approach put forth by Wei et al. [31] that is built on CNN. Advanced data augmentation and transfer learning algorithms were used to enhance the classification performance after taking into account prior information based on cancer class and subclass. Between 97.64% and 97.97% accuracy was attained in separating benign from malignant pictures. For classifying breast cancer histopathology pictures into benign or malignant, Pratiher et al. [32] presented a cascaded strategy based on manifold learning L-ISOMAP and stacked

sparse auto-encoder. The reported outcomes ranged from 96.8% to 98.2%. Breast histopathology pictures can be classified as benign or malignant using CNN features, local, and frequency domain features, according to Nahid et al. [33]. Their general accuracy ranged from 94.40% to 97.19%. The same authors presented other deep learning strategies in [34] that were aided by K-Means and Mean-Shift local clustering algorithms. They tested both Softmax and Support Vector Machine (SVM) as output classifiers and used CNN and Long-Short-Term Memory (LSTM) as main building models. The classification of benign and malignant conditions had the highest reported accuracy, which ranged between 90% and 91%. A comparison of the classification performance of handcrafted features and deep features was made by Bardou et al. [35]. While deep features were produced by training a CNN from scratch, handcrafted features were encoded using a bag of words and locality-constrained linear coding before being categorised using SVM. The most accurate results were based on CNN and ranged from 83.31% to 88.23% for multi-class classification and between 96.15% and 98.33% for binary classification. Overall, the research discussed above demonstrated a clear preference for using deep CNNs for the categorization of histological images of breast cancer due to their much improved performance. However, it is not simple to train a deep CNN because it needs a lot of CPU and memory resources and frequently encounters convergence and overfitting issues. In this context, a recent study by Tajbakhsh et al. [36] shows that a well-tuned CNN performs better than the one trained from scratch or, in the worst scenario, as well as it in medical image processing (computed tomography (CT), ultrasonography, and optical endoscopy). The research for the histopathological imaging modality was expanded by Shallu et al. [37]. They noticed that a fine-tuned VGG-16 [38] with a logistic regression classifier had produced better classification results by achieving an accuracy of 92.60% for MI binary classification when compared to a S. Boumaraf et al. Biomedical Signal Processing and Control 63 (2021) 1021923 CNN trained from scratch. In [39], the same authors described a CNN model with three convolutional layers, a max pooling layer, and two fully-connected layers that they fully trained to achieve an accuracy of 85.3% for MI binary classification. To categorise MI breast histopathology pictures into benign or malignant, Xiang et al. [40] tested a fine-tuned Inception-v3 [41] and reported an overall accuracy of 95.7%.

A. *Handcrafted ML Based Computer-Aided Diagnosis*

For the purpose of choosing the best ways to apply the CAD system, medical image processing requires prior knowledge of the content and nature of the image. Effective image processing techniques must be used in the major stages of the CAD system in order to obtain a high level of efficiency for automated diagnostics. CAD systems typically include five steps, as indicated in Fig 3. The following is a basic explanation of the key steps in a CAD system: (1) Image pre-processing :- Some imaging modalities, including ultrasound, depend on this step to improve the image and minimise noise while minimising feature distortion. There may not be a pre-processing stage in some CAD programmes. (2) Image segmentation:- A crucial stage in the effective development of CAD systems is image segmentation. The separation of the region of interest (ROI) in accordance with the desired properties is the primary goal of segmentation. In recent years, 3D images have been made possible by a variety of imaging modalities, including computed tomography (CT), 3D ultrasound, and many more. As a result, 3D segmentation techniques are preferred for volumetric picture segmentation that is more precise. (3) Feature extraction and selection:- In this step, several features are taken from the image in accordance with the characteristics of the lesions. These characteristics

help distinguish between benign and malignant tumours. The feature set is typically fairly large, and the following stage depends greatly on the choice of the best features. (4) Classification:- The suspicious areas are categorised as benign or malignant using various classification techniques based on the chosen criteria. This section presents the typical classification techniques used in medical imaging. (5) Performance evaluation:- The effectiveness of the CAD system is assessed in this step.

The data extracted from the selected articles about different machine-learning techniques are presented in Table 4, which shows the machine-learning methods for disease prediction. The table summarizes existing literature articles collected in this survey using machine learning methods to manage breast cancer disease. The first column refers to the technique; the second column is the employed machine learning method to identify the benefit; and finally, the last column identifies the drawbacks.

TABLE 4
DIFFERENT MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES TO MANAGE BREAST CANCER DISEASES

Technique	Benefits	Drawbacks
Logistic Regression[42]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It can offer probability. 2. To categorise new data using continuous and discrete datasets. 3. They are used to categorise the observations based on various forms of data. 4. Identify the classification variables that are most useful in a timely manner. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There must be a categorical dependent variable. 2. Multicollinearity should not exist in the independent variable.
Support Vector Machine or SVM[43]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Classify the n-dimensional space to establish the decision boundary. 2. Future placement of the new data point in the appropriate class will be simple. 3. It finds the closest point of the lines from both classes. 4. SVM aims to maximize this margin. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not appropriate for massive data sets. 2. SVM might function more effectively if the data set contains more noise. 3. Choosing an appropriate kernel function is complex.
K-Nearest Neighbor(KNN) Algorithm[44]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Easily identify the group or class of a particular dataset. 2. Resistant to jittery training data. 3. More efficient if there is a large amount of training data. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. K's value must always be determined, which might be tricky at times. 2. The high computation cost is caused by the need to calculate the distance between each data point for each training sample.
Decision Trees[45]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simple to understand as it follows a human's process while making real-life decisions. 2. It may be useful for resolving issues involving decisions. 3. Taking into account all potential solutions to an issue is helpful. 4. In comparison to other methods, there is less room for data cleansing. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The decision tree is complicated since it has many nodes. 2. It can have an issue with overfitting. 3. For more class labels, the computational complexity of the decision tree could rise.
Random Forest[45]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Both classification and regression tasks can 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It is inappropriate for regression tasks.

	<p>be carried out by Random Forest.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> It is able to manage big datasets with lots of dimensions. It eliminates the overfitting problem and improves the model's accuracy. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> It requires much more time to train as compared to decision trees.
Principal Component Analysis (PCA)[46]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Mostly used to reduce the data's dimensionality. Using the largest variance vectors, the algorithms condense the amount of features to 3 or 4. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> It may need to include some information compared to the original list of features. Compared to original features, principal components are harder to read and understand. Before using PCA, standardise your data; otherwise, PCA won't be able to identify the best principal components.

B. Learned DL Based Computer-Aided Diagnosis [47]

Artificial neural networks have been improved or updated with deep learning techniques [48, 49], which take advantage of plentiful, affordable computing. They are focused on creating larger or more intricate neural networks. Massive collections containing labelled analogue data, such as images, text, audio, and video, are a focus of several techniques. Convolutional Neural Network, Recurrent Neural Network, Long Short-Term Memory Network, Stacked Auto-Encoders, Deep Boltzmann Machine, and Deep Belief Network are the common deep learning algorithms [26, 33]. A DL-based CAD system is shown in Fig. 3. The following layers are implemented by CAD system based on CNN: (1) Convolutional operations that automatically extract features from the image use convolutional layers. (2) Dimensionality reduction of features using a pooling layer (3) Fully connected and Softmax layer for classification.

Figure 3. Machine learning and deep learning framework

C. Comparative Analysis Based On Classification Algorithms Of Machine Learning

This section includes a comparative analysis of various machine learning classifiers used by authors to diagnose breast cancer. Table 5 provides a summary of some of the well-known studies on the diagnosis of breast cancer.

TABLE 5
COMPARATIVE STUDY ON MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

Dataset	Method Used	Performance Measure	Pros	Cons	Reference
DDSM database	GA +S3VM	Acc-92.1 % (Gaussian), 87.37% (Triangle), 89.55% (Linear)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Semi-supervised classification 2. GA reduces feature vector dimensionality 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Low performance classification 	[50]
Wisconsin Breast Cancer Database	GBN,SVM, KNN, LDA,QDA,LR, ET, AB,GB, DT,RF	Acc-98.23%(AB), 95.57%(GB),93.80%(DT), 96.45(RF),95.57%(GBN),51.10%(SVM),91.11%(KNN), 95.33%(LDA), 96.51%(QDA), 94.63% (LR), 97.34 %(ET)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GB resolves hyperparameter problem 2. Control parameter setting and automated cancer diagnosis 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suitable for numerical and categorical values 	[51]
MIAS dataset, DDSM dataset	CDTM + KPCA + GOA-KELM	Acc- 97.49% (MIAS) Acc- 92.61% (DDSM)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Better classification accuracy 2. Reduced number of features 3. Multi-class classification 4. Minimum computational time 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Images from CT, ultrasound, and thermography can't be considered. 2. No deep learning approaches 	[49]
WBCD dataset	Least Square SVM (LS-SVM)	Acc-97.08	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Examining medical information in less time 2. Exploration of data 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Built as a system for offline diagnosis 	[52]
UCI machine learning repository	SVM and SVM ensembles (Linear kernel and RBF kernel)	Acc-96.85%,ROC- 0.967, F-measure -0.966 (GA + linear SVM), F-measure -0.988(GA + RBF SVM), Acc-98.28%(GA + RBF SVM ensemble), ROC- 0.98(GA + linear SVM ensembles and GA + poly SVM ensembles), Acc-99.52% ROC-0.876, F-measure-0.995 (GA + linear SVM ensembles and RBF SVM ensembles)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Better performance for SVM ensembles 2. Small-scale datasets perform better with RBF kernel-based SVM ensembles with the boosting approach and linear kernel-based SVM ensembles based on the bagging method. 3. RBF kernel-based SVM ensembles with boosting-based training perform better for large datasets. 4. After feature selection, a significant reduction in the computational time for SVM classifiers 5. The RBF SVM and poly SVM have the shortest training times, respectively. 6. The linear SVM classifier requires a lot of computing time. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Baseline classifier(s) cannot be distinguished from the superior prediction model(s) 	[53]
BreaKHis dataset	Sliding window technique+ LBP+ SVM + Majority voting technique	Acc- 91.12%, Sn- 85.22%, and Sp- 94.01%.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sliding window for better generalization 2. Fast and effective feature extraction 3. From images of histopathology slide, finely detailed features were retrieved using the fusion of sliding window approach and LBP. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No comparison of various machine learning techniques. 	[54]

WBCD data set	SVM and KNN	Acc- 98.57% Sp- 95.65% (SVM) Acc- 97.14% Sp- 92.31% (K-Nearest Neighbors)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Helpful to both the general public and the medical staff 2. Supervised ML techniques use attribute training 3. Uses 10-fold cross-validation 4. Better results 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Numerical and categorical values. 	[48]
WDBC and BCCD datasets	SVM, LR, KNN, and ensemble classifier	Acc-99.3% (Polynomial SVM) Acc-98.06% (LR) Acc-97.35% (KNN) Acc- 97.61% (Ensemble classifier) for WDBC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shorter training time 2. High accuracy for SVM polynomial kernel 3. LR with recursive feature elimination has higher accuracy. 4. DE (data exploratory) techniques effectively detect higher accuracy 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unable to provide malignant features 2. Non-effective results for BCCD dataset 3. Not effective with the Asian patients 4. No deep learning methods 	[55]
Images taken using ultrasound technology at the Breast Cancer Unit at the Oncology Specialist Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq	ANN	Prec - 82.04% Sn - 79.39% Sp - 84.75%	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High positive predicate rates 2. Using the ultrasound images, a variety of texture features were retrieved. 3. ANN classifiers can address a heterogeneous mix of disorders using a single ultrasound image from each patient. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The automatic segmentation becomes difficult due to the extreme variance in tumour size, location, and shape. 2. Restrict the feature extraction 3. Limited number of data 	[56]
Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset from UCI Repository	RF, PCA+R, KNN, ANN, PCA+ANN, NB	Kappa-0.91,acc-0.95, sn-0.92,sp0.98(RF), Kappa-0.95,acc-0.95, sn-0.92,sp-0.97(PCA+RF), Kappa-0.93,acc-0.97,sn-0.92,sp-1(KNN),Kappa-0.93,acc-0.97,sn-0.92, sp-1(ANN) Kappa-0.93,acc-0.97, sn-0.95,sp-0.98 (PCA+ANN),Kappa-0.81,acc-0.91,sn-0.88,sp-0.92(NB)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Combine multivariate statistical and machine learning techniques 2. PCA measures variance in data 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High performance for binary classification 	[57]

D. Comparative Study Using Deep Learning Classification Methods

The advancements made in recent years for using deep learning to diagnose breast cancer are presented in this section. Table 6 provides an overview of some deep learning-based research on the diagnosis of breast cancer.

TABLE 6
COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHMS

Dataset	Method Used	Performance Measure	Pros	Cons	Reference
BACH dataset	EMS-Net	Acc -91.75% (training images) Acc-90.00% (testing images)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Patch augmentation and fine-tuning pre-trained DCNN 2. Fast testing 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Non identified and discriminative image regions 2. Time-consuming in training stage 	[58]
ABUS image dataset from Jeonbuk National University Hospital (JNUH).	Inception-v3 CNN	Sn-88.6% Sp-87.6% AUC- 0.9468 ±0.0164	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Learns the image features from raw images 2. CNN for feature extraction and classification 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No dedicated algorithms for breast lesion detection and classification 	[59]

<p>Digital Database for Screening Mammography (DDSM) from the Massachusetts General Hospital (D. Kopans, R. Moore), the University of South Florida (K. Bowyer), and the Sandia National Laboratories (P. Kegelmeyer).</p>	<p>DCNN+GLCM+HOT + XGBoost DCNN+GLCM+HOT + SVM</p>	<p>Acc is 9.96% to Acc- 92.80% (XGBoost) Acc-84%(malignant tumors, XGBoost)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. DCNN is used as a feature extractor 2. GLCM and HOT are used to extract breast mass information 3. SVM and XGBoost for classification 4. XGBoost deals with a limited number of available training samples and texture features 5. XGBoost handles imbalanced training data 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Low volume dataset 	<p>[60]</p>
<p>Dataset from the India's Visakhapatnam-based M. G. Cancer Hospital & Research Institute</p>	<p>DNNS</p>	<p>Acc-97.21% Pre- 97.9% Rec-97.01%</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Image performance, effectiveness, and quality are improved with normalization. 2. Based on a deep neural network's support value 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not evaluate CNN features 	<p>[61]</p>
<p>INBREAST and CBIS-DDSM DATABASES</p>	<p>Deep CNN+RGP , Deep CNN+GGP</p>	<p>Acc- 0.919 ± 0.0003 AUC- 0.934 ± 0.0003 (RGP , INBREAST DATABASE) Acc-0.922 ± 0.0002 AUC- 0.924 ± 0.0003 (GGP ,INBREAST DATABASE) Acc-0.762 ± 0.0002 AUC- 0.838 ± 0.0001 (RGP, CBIS-DDSM DATABASE) Acc-0.767 ± 0.0002 AUC- 0.823 ± 0.0002 (GGP, CBIS-DDSM DATABASE)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. RGP and GGP structures were used for learning features 2. Numerous irrelevant regions are eliminated. 3. DNN to extract hierarchical features 4. Find potentially dangerous areas roughly 5. Automatic annotation to reduce the cost of annotations 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Limited number of samples. 2. Low performance classification 	<p>[62]</p>
<p>BreaKHis dataset</p>	<p>GCN+ ResNet-18+Transfer learning,+Three-fold Data Augmentation</p>	<p>Acc-98.08% - 99.25% (MD binary classification) Acc-89.56%- 94.49% (MD eight-class classification) Acc- 98.42% (Binary MI classification) Acc-92.03% (Eight-class MI classification)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The binary and eight-class classifications for both Magnification Dependent (MD) and Magnification Independent (MI) may be addressed in an efficient manner. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Colour differences in breast images have less of an impact when stain-color normalisation procedures are absent. 2. Low performance of eight-class classification 3. Need to mix handcrafted characteristics with deep CNN intrinsic features 	<p>[63]</p>
<p>Dataset from LRH hospital Peshawar, Pakistan</p>	<p>GoogLeNet , VGGNet and ResNet, Transfer Learning</p>	<p>Acc- 93.5% (GoogLeNet) Acc- 94.15% (VGGNet) Acc-94.35% (ResNet) Acc- 97.525%</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transfer learning utilizes the gained knowledge for improving accuracy 2. Pre-trained CNN is used to extract features from images. 3. A data set's size is increased by data augmentation to increase CNN's effectiveness. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Not evaluate the model with hand-crafted features + CNN features to improve the classification accuracy 	<p>[64]</p>

III. EVALUATION METRICS [65]

- A. *Confusion Matrix*: It is one of the estimates used to assess a model's performance when the outcome can include two or more groups. It indicates the relationship between predicted and actual values (Fig 4).

		Predicted Classes	
		Negative	Positive
Actual Classes	Negative	True Negative	False Positive
	Positive	False Negative	True Positive

Figure 4. Confusion Matrix

True negative (T.N.)— patients with negative diagnoses actually are negative.

False positive (F.P.)— patients who have been given a positive diagnosis yet are actually negative.

False negative (F.N.)— patients with negative diagnoses who are actually positive.

True positive (T.P.)— patients diagnosed positive and are genuinely positive.

- B. *Accuracy*: It is calculated as the proportion of correctly classified samples to all samples and is denoted as follows:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

- C. *Precision/Positive Predicted Value (PPV)*: Indicates the proportion of patients who are relevant (+ve) and described as:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

- D. *Sensitivity/Recall/True Positive Rate (TPR)*: It assesses the proportion of patients who are accurately diagnosed as having a specific disease (+positive cases), and is demonstrated as:

$$\text{Sensitivity (recall)} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

- E. *Specificity/True Negative Rate (TNR)*: Identifies the percentages of individuals who are appropriately excluded from having a specific condition (-ve occurrences) and is explained as:

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

- F. *False-Positive Rate (FPR)*: If the outcome is negative, it forecasts a positive value. FPR is hence 1-specificity and is given as:

$$\text{FPR} = \frac{FP}{TN + FP}$$

- G. *True-Positive Rate (TPR)*: When the outcome is positive, it makes a positive value prediction. Accordingly, TPR is provided as follows:

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

H. *F-measure*: Described as the harmonic mean of recall and precision, it can be defined as follows:

$$F\text{-measure} = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

I. *Log loss or cross-entropy loss*: To calculate the model's performance, probability estimates are used, and the results are given as:

$$\text{Logloss} = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n ((\log(p_i) * y_i) + (\log(1 - p_i) * (1 - y_i)))$$

n: a dataset's total number of points

p_i: the anticipated likelihood of the ith point

y_i: class label for the real output

J. *AUC (Area Under Curve) and ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) Curve*: The Area Under Curve (AUC) is a measure of a classifier's ability to differentiate between classes. A higher AUC indicates better performance at distinct threshold points. The X-axis in a ROC curve represents the False Positive Rate (FPR), indicating the proportion of false positives. The Y-axis represents the True Positive Rate (TPR), indicating the proportion of true positives. A higher X-value means more false positives compared to true negatives, while a higher Y-value means more true positives compared to false negatives.

IV. RESEARCH NEEDS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Worldwide, the prevalence of breast cancer is rising at an alarming rate, and long-term survival depends on early detection and diagnosis. The best method for early diagnosis and therapy has been demonstrated to be CAD image analysis of medical images. When employing deep learning and machine learning to diagnose breast cancer, there are a few major issues that must be resolved [66].

A. *Data Pre-processing*

To increase the quality of the data used for machine learning, data pre-processing [67] is an essential step. We must pre-process input data before supplying it to our model since the crucial information it extracts directly affects its capacity to learn. Standardisation is a crucial part of the pre-processing phase. When we standardise our data, we change the numbers so that the mean and normal deviation are both 0. Another crucial component of data pre-processing is handling categorical variables. The variables that are discrete and not continuous are known as categorical variables. When features in our dataset are highly interdependent, multi-collinearity occurs, making it impossible to determine the relevance of the features using a weight vector. The interpretability of our model is impacted by multi-collinearity in the pre-processing of the data.

B. *Feature Extraction*

Feature extraction [67] automatically reduces the dimensionality [66] of observations into a much smaller set and is modeled it. Predictive modelling algorithms can't directly model some observations since they are significantly too voluminous in their raw form, like image, audio, and textual data. However, tabular data with millions of properties might be included just as quickly. Include projection techniques for tabular data, such as unsupervised clustering and principal component analysis (PCA). Additionally, the image data employs edge or line detection.

Observations provide many of the same digital signal processing methods depending on the domain, whether an image, video, or audio. The key to feature extraction is that the methods are automatic, address the issue of too high dimensional data, and are frequently used to analogue observations saved in digital formats. Whenever a data scientist plays with a dataset of many variables, there are chances that some of them are redundant or noisy. That means such variables do not carry any signal useful as a predictor. Noise, as always, affects the overall accuracy of any predictive model.

C. Massive And Imbalanced Dataset

The magnitude of the data could lead to problems with generalisation, data imbalance, and difficulty achieving the global optimum [24]. In summary, sparse approximation is often seen when there is a lack of training data. This can lead to poor performance, which can stem from two scenarios: an under-constrained model that overfits the sparse training dataset or an over-constrained model that underfits the training dataset. Insufficient test data contributes to an overly optimistic and high variance estimation of model performance. Machine Learning algorithms generally produce inadmissible classifiers when confronted with imbalanced datasets. A large portion of this present reality arrangement issue shows some class awkwardness, which happens when inadequate information relates to both class names.

D. Learning Strategy

Algorithms for supervised learning [68] examine labelled data in which the proper classifications are determined to learn particular analytical patterns. The unsupervised learning algorithm works independently to find a new model or pattern that might not be apparent to the human eye rather than being guided by labelled data. When working with large datasets devoid of underlying structure, unsupervised learning is very useful for data mining. In datasets that you need assistance understanding or figuring out what to do with, it can help you identify patterns and meanings. Unsupervised learning is a computationally intensive technique; when coupled, it identifies the structures that act as training material for the supervised learning process.

E. Model Selection

Model selection [66] is the way toward picking one of the models as the final learn model that tends to the issue. The best way to deal with model selection requires adequate information, which might be almost vast and liable to the problem's complicated nature. One of the critical decisions to be made in the model selection procedure relates to our presumption about the shape of the functional relationship between the input variable and the response variable. When we decide to accept the shape of our model, we develop a parametric model, and our concern lessens to assessing many quantifiable elements, known as parameters. The most popular assumptions are that the data is linear. While we can loosen up the linear assumption when fundamental, we, once in a while, don't have any desire to expect the shape of the function by any means. Non-parametric models help to maintain a strategic distance from the situation where we erroneously expect a function that doesn't match the data. In any case, many perceptions are acquired to make non-parametric techniques successful, which can be expensive or even infeasible.

Notwithstanding the way that non-parametric strategies are regularly not practical, there are different trade-offs to contemplate. One critical trade-off is between interpretability and adaptability. Since non-parametric models follow the data cautiously, they periodically bring about unusually shaped plots, which can be challenging to interpret. Suppose the objective is to comprehend and demonstrate the connection between the input and output variables. In

that case, we might be eager to exchange some predictive power for a parametric curve that is increasingly reasonable. Another fundamental trade-off is that of variance versus bias [15].

V. CONCLUSION

The research survey looks at disease diagnosis using different machine learning methods, including regression, SVM, deep learning, decision trees, random forests, and K-NN. The study recommends comparing techniques to create an efficient algorithm for pattern classification for multiple classes. Machine learning algorithms can detect hidden patterns for classification from a large dataset, making them useful for medical diagnosis. The review aims to answer several research questions, such as existing techniques for disease diagnosis and problems solved using ML and DL algorithms. Machine learning is essential in detecting cancer diagnosis, and the timely automated prediction of specific patterns ensures better resource utilization in biomedical fields. The development of clustering, noise removal, and fuzzy rule-based algorithms for breast cancer disease identification is still required, nevertheless.

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